

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15735035

Audit Committee Size And Corporate Value: A Comparative Study of Nigerian and Ghanaian Listed Companies

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of audit committee size on corporate value: a comparative study of Nigerian and Ghanaian listed companies. The study adopted ex post facto research design. The population of the study consists of twenty one (21) listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria and six (6) listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Ghana. The study used equal sample size of six (6) consumer goods manufacturing companies from both countries. Secondary data was obtained from the audited annual financial reports of listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria and Ghana from 2014-2023. Hypothesis formulated was tested using panel least squares regression with the aid of E-views 12 econometric statistical software. Finding showed that audit committee size with a negative beta coefficient of (-444.10) and a statistically significant p-value of (0.01), has a significant negative effect on firm value in Nigeria and with a positive beta coefficient of (0.34) and a statistically significant p-value of (0.01), has a significant positive effect on firm value in Ghana. In conclusion, the effectiveness of audit committee size is not universal but context-dependent, influenced by institutional, regulatory, and organizational dynamics unique to each country. Given the negative impact of larger audit committees on firm value of listed Nigerian firms, we recommend that regulators and boards should evaluate and potentially enforce limits on the maximum size of audit committees to improve efficiency and accountability.

Keywords: Audit Committee Size, Firm Value, Nigerian Firms, Ghanaian Firms

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance has emerged as a critical area of focus for enhancing the transparency, accountability, and overall performance of firms, especially in emerging markets. Audit committees, as integral components of corporate governance structures, play a pivotal role in overseeing financial reporting, internal controls, and risk management processes. Their effectiveness directly influences the reliability of financial statements and the trust of investors and stakeholders (Surya et al., 2021). In recent years, both Nigeria and Ghana have made significant strides in improving their corporate governance frameworks. According to Gbenyi et al. (2023), regulatory bodies such as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) of Nigeria and the Ghanaian Securities and Exchange Commission have issued guidelines emphasizing the need for robust audit committee structures. Despite these efforts, challenges

such as inconsistent enforcement and resource constraints continue to hinder the full realization of effective governance practices (Okpara, 2011).

Corporate governance mechanisms are critical for safeguarding shareholder interests (Nwafor & Nworie, 2025) and enhancing firm value. Among these mechanisms, the audit committee plays a pivotal role in overseeing financial reporting processes, internal controls, and risk management practices. The size of the audit committee has emerged as a significant factor influencing the effectiveness of this oversight function. An optimally sized audit committee is believed to improve monitoring quality, reduce information asymmetry, and thereby contribute positively to corporate value (Iheyen, 2021). However, the relationship between audit committee size and firm value is far from straightforward, especially in emerging markets such as Nigeria and Ghana where corporate governance practices continue to evolve under regulatory reforms and market pressures.

The nexus between audit committee size and firm value has garnered significant attention in corporate governance research, particularly in the context of developing economies. Audit committee size is integral to ensuring the integrity of financial reporting and effective oversight, which are critical for enhancing firm value (Amer & Shehata, 2014; Raweh et al., 2019). Audit committee effectiveness is acknowledged as a vital element of corporate governance, playing a key role in monitoring financial reporting and maintaining the accuracy of financial statements. In Nigeria and Ghana, incidents of corporate failures and financial scandals have heightened doubts about whether audit committee characteristics are sufficient to protect the interests of stakeholders. For example, in Nigeria, the collapse of companies like Cadbury Nigeria Plc has been linked, in part, to shortcomings in corporate governance frameworks, particularly involving underperforming audit committees.

Effective audit committees require a balance—too few members might limit diverse expertise and monitoring capacity, while too many can hinder communication, decision-making efficiency, and accountability (Iheyen, 2021). Empirical evidence on the ideal audit committee size remains mixed. Some scholars argue that larger audit committees enhance monitoring by bringing varied financial expertise and diverse perspectives, ultimately improving firm performance and value (Sharma & Iselin, 2012). Conversely, others contend that increasing the number of members may dilute individual accountability, foster coordination challenges, and potentially elevate the risk of financial misreporting. In Nigeria, for instance, the Corporate Governance Code recommends a minimum of three independent non-executive directors on the audit committee, while the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) limits the size to no more than six members. Yet, in practice, variations exist due to firm size, ownership structure, and regulatory enforcement.

As a result, a suboptimal committee may fail to detect or prevent financial irregularities, undermining investor confidence and negatively impacting firm valuation. It is severally argued that larger audit committees were paradoxically associated with a higher risk of financial misreporting, suggesting that mere expansion in numbers does not guarantee improved oversight (Sharma & Iselin, 2012). Meanwhile, studies like Kirui (2022) highlight that committees enriched with financial expertise can enhance analyst perceptions and firm value, underscoring the importance of member quality alongside quantity. The divergent findings across contexts emphasize the need for a comparative examination of audit committee size and its effect on corporate value within Nigerian and Ghanaian listed firms, where governance structures and regulatory environments differ yet share emerging market challenges.

1.1 Objective of the Study

The study aims to examine the effect of audit committee size on corporate value: a comparative study of Nigerian and Ghanaian listed companies.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Audit committee size and firm value

Audit committee size refers to the number of individuals serving on a company's audit committee, typically composed of independent non-executive directors (Grange et al., 2021). It influences the

effectiveness of oversight, with both too few and too many members potentially impairing decision-making and monitoring functions. The size is often guided by corporate governance codes, aiming to strike a balance between expertise, independence, and efficiency. Firm value represents the total worth of a business as perceived by investors and is often measured through metrics such as market capitalization (Anaike et al., 2025), or Tobin's (Ukoh et al., 2024). It reflects the firm's ability to generate sustainable profits, manage risks, and deliver long-term returns to shareholders. Corporate governance structures, including audit committee effectiveness, can significantly impact firm value by enhancing transparency and investor confidence.

Amer et al., (2014) discussed that the Blue-Ribbon Committee, through the SEC's 1999 mandate, required audit committee composition to include at least three directors. Their study found that audit committee size did not significantly influence firm performance in Egypt. Agyemang-Mintah and Schadewitz (2017) suggested that audit committees should have a minimum of three members, or two in smaller companies, consisting of independent, experienced, and ethically reputable non-executive directors to protect shareholders' interests in financial reporting and internal control. Raweh et al., (2019) concurred, emphasizing that audit committees should include at least three members, one of whom should be a financial expert and an independent chairman. Nehme (2015) found that larger audit committees tend to increase the audit report lag, while Karajeh and Ibrahim (2017) advocated for larger committees to ensure diverse experiences and skills for effective monitoring and financial reporting oversight.

Zraq and Fadzil (2018) reported a positive relationship between audit committee size and company financial performance, supported by Hamdan et al., (2013), who found a significant positive correlation in the financial sector listed on the Amman Stock Exchange Market. Zubair (2016) identified a statistically significant positive correlation between the size of the audit committee and key performance indicators—namely, return on assets (ROA), net interest margin, and Tobin's Q—in Nigeria's listed deposit money banks. This suggests that larger audit committees may contribute positively to financial oversight and operational efficiency in the banking sector. In a related study, Orjinta and Ikuze (2018) also reported a positive and significant association between audit committee size and firm performance, particularly within the context of non-financial companies. Their findings reinforce the notion that an expanded audit committee can enhance governance practices and support improved corporate outcomes across various sectors. Madi et al., (2014) indicated that audit committee size significantly affects corporate voluntary disclosure. Asiriwa, et al (2018) observed a positive significant relationship between audit committee size and audit quality.

However, Olayinka (2019) noted no significant effect of audit committee size on firm performance. Al-Matari et al. (2012) found a negative influence of audit committee size on firm performance in Saudi Arabian companies. Al-Sayani (2020) discovered no relationship between Impression Management (IM) and audit committee size, warning that larger committees might lead to passive participation, thereby undermining decision-making and monitoring functions (Lipton & Lorsch, 1992). Despite these divergent views, a consensus suggests that a sufficiently large audit committee prevents overburdening its members, ensuring thorough and reliable work to enhance firm value.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical underpinning of the research is the Agency theory. The theory was originally introduced by Jensen and Meckling in 1976, and it provides a theoretical foundation for understanding the dynamics between shareholders (principals) and company executives or managers (agents) (Nworie & Obi, 2024). It highlights the potential for conflicts of interest that arise when control of a company is separated from its ownership—an idea that dates back to Adam Smith's early observations about corporate governance. When managers act on behalf of shareholders but do not directly bear the consequences of their decisions, they may prioritize personal goals over shareholder value, leading to what is termed “agency costs.”

This theory is particularly relevant in corporate governance studies focused on emerging markets such as Nigeria and Ghana, where governance frameworks continue to mature. Prior research (e.g., Karajeh & Ibrahim, 2017; Mohammed, 2016) has shown that managerial opportunism—such as manipulating

financial reports—can undermine firm value when oversight is weak. However, mechanisms like audit committees are crucial in curbing such behaviors. Well-structured audit committees, particularly those with the right size, independence, and financial expertise, are essential in mitigating agency problems by enhancing oversight, promoting transparency, and reducing information asymmetry between management and shareholders.

In this context, audit committee size becomes a critical variable. A properly sized audit committee can enhance its effectiveness in monitoring management, while a poorly sized one—either too small to offer diversity of opinion or too large to maintain focus and accountability—may fail to serve its purpose. Consequently, understanding how audit committee size influences firm value in Nigerian and Ghanaian listed companies offers useful hints into how corporate governance mechanisms can be optimized to reduce agency conflicts and improve overall firm performance.

2.3 Empirical Review

Osi, Jerry, and Mark (2024) examined the influence of audit committee characteristics on the financial performance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The study employed panel least square regression on data from 10 firms spanning 2015 to 2021. Among the various audit committee attributes investigated, including size, independence, gender diversity, meeting frequency, and financial expertise, only financial expertise showed a significant positive impact on return on assets (ROA). Audit committee size exhibited a positive but statistically insignificant effect, suggesting its limited role in enhancing firm performance within this sector.

Abu et al. (2024) conducted a study on the relationship between audit committee characteristics and the financial performance of industrial goods firms quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Utilizing generalized least squares with random effects on 13 firms over the period 2013–2022, the analysis focused on audit committee size, independence, and frequency of meetings. Results indicated that audit committee size had a positive but insignificant effect on ROA and ROE, while independence had a significantly negative impact on ROA. This suggests that merely increasing audit committee size does not automatically translate into enhanced firm performance, especially when other dynamics like independence play a more influential role.

Umoru, Oziegbe, and Bekweri (2024) explored the audit committee attributes affecting financial performance in Nigeria's oil and gas sector. Using a panel least squares regression model, the study analyzed data on audit committee size, independence, gender diversity, meeting frequency, and financial expertise. Although audit committee financial expertise was positively and significantly associated with financial performance, audit committee size—along with the other variables—had a positive but insignificant effect. This finding indicates that audit committee size, while directionally aligned with improved performance, may not be a decisive factor on its own.

Gbenyi et al. (2023) investigated the effect of audit committee characteristics on the share price reactions of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Applying a pooled autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model, the study incorporated variables like audit committee size, independence, expertise, frequency of meetings, and gender diversity. Interestingly, the results showed a perverse but significant effect of audit committee size on share price reaction, implying that larger audit committees may be perceived unfavorably by investors. The study raises concerns about possible inefficiencies or coordination challenges in larger audit committees within the banking sector.

Orife et al. (2022) assessed how audit committee attributes influence financial reporting quality among selected oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Their panel regression analysis covered data from 2011 to 2020 and considered variables such as size, busyness, gender diversity, and independence. The findings revealed a positive relationship between audit committee size and the timeliness of financial reporting, indicating that larger committees might help in improving reporting efficiency. However, other factors such as busyness and gender diversity were negatively associated with reporting quality, suggesting that committee composition and workload must be carefully managed.

Afenya et al. (2022) focused on the impact of audit committee characteristics on audit fees in Ghana. Their regression analysis examined attributes such as audit committee size, meeting frequency, expertise, and gender diversity. The study found that all these attributes, including size, had a significantly negative impact on audit fees. This suggests that larger audit committees may lead to cost efficiencies, possibly due to improved internal control processes or negotiation leverage with external auditors.

Omotoye et al. (2021) analyzed the relationship between audit committee and board attributes and the market performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, using both fixed and random effects regression models. The results indicated a significantly negative association between audit committee size and market performance measured by Tobin's Q. While gender diversity and expertise positively influenced performance, audit committee size appeared detrimental. This highlights the need for balance in committee structuring, as oversized committees may dilute effectiveness and decision-making speed.

Dim and Joshua (2021) investigated how audit committee attributes affect firm value among Nigerian financial firms using a dynamic panel GMM model. The study incorporated audit committee size, independence, gender diversity, and expertise as variables, with firm value measured by Tobin's Q and EVA. Audit committee size showed a positive and significant influence on firm value, suggesting that larger committees might offer broader oversight capabilities. However, the effectiveness of such committees may depend on complementary factors like expertise and meeting frequency.

Iheyen (2021) focused on listed insurance companies in Nigeria to determine the influence of audit committee attributes on firm value. Using OLS regression, the study found that audit committee size and remuneration negatively influenced Tobin's Q, while independence had a positive effect. The negative effect of size implies that beyond a certain threshold, additional committee members might hinder rather than help performance. These results suggest the importance of optimal sizing tailored to the firm's complexity and industry.

Dakhlallh et al. (2020) examined Jordanian firms over a 14-year period to understand how audit committee size and other characteristics affect firm performance, using Tobin's Q as a metric. The multiple regression analysis showed that audit committee size had a positive and significant impact on firm performance. Alongside size, independence and financial expertise also positively influenced outcomes, while stock ownership by audit committee members showed a negative relationship. The study provides strong evidence that well-structured and adequately sized audit committees can enhance corporate governance effectiveness in emerging markets.

2.4 Gap in Literature

In spite of the extensive empirical investigations into the role of audit committee size on firm performance and value, the literature presents mixed and context-specific findings, underscoring the need for a comparative analysis across different national contexts. While studies like those of Osi et al. (2024), Abu (2024), and Umoru et al. (2024) report a positive but statistically insignificant effect of audit committee size on financial performance in Nigerian firms, Omotoye et al. (2021) and Iheyen (2021) found a significantly negative impact on market performance and firm value, suggesting potential inefficiencies in larger committees. Conversely, Dakhlallh et al. (2020), focusing on Jordan, and Afenya et al. (2022), studying Ghana, provide evidence of a significantly positive influence of audit committee size on firm performance and cost efficiency. This divergence in findings raises questions about whether the effect of audit committee size is influenced by institutional, regulatory, or economic differences between countries. To date, no known study has conducted a direct comparative analysis between Nigeria and Ghana—two key West African economies—on the impact of audit committee size on corporate value, leaving a significant gap in the literature regarding regional governance dynamics and their implications for corporate performance.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study employed a longitudinal ex post facto research design to assess the effect of audit committee size on firm value among listed firms in Nigeria and Ghana. The ex post facto approach is appropriate for

research that examines causal relationships based on historical data, particularly when it is neither feasible nor ethical to manipulate the variables under study. In this case, the audit committee structure and corporate value data are derived from company records that already exist and cannot be altered, making ex-post facto research design a suitable tool for the study (Nworie & Orji-Okafor, 2024; et al., Nworie et al., 2022). This design supports causal inference without experimental control, making it well-suited to a study that investigates the relationship between governance mechanisms and corporate performance over time. The longitudinal component was included to observe trends across multiple years. This enables the study to assess how audit committee size influences corporate value over time while capturing both cross-sectional and time-series dimensions.

The population for this study consisted of consumer goods manufacturing firms listed on the NGX and GSE as of 2023. In Nigeria, there were 21 such companies, while in Ghana, 6 firms met the criteria. Only companies with complete, accessible, and consistent data on audit committee size and firm value for the ten-year study period (2014–2023) were considered. Firms were selected based on the availability of verifiable financial statements, governance disclosures, and market data.

To allow for balanced cross-country analysis, the study employed a purposive sampling technique to select six firms each from Nigeria and Ghana, resulting in a total sample of 12 firms. The choice to use an equal number of firms from both countries was deliberate, aimed at improving the comparability of findings across national contexts. The final sample included only firms that had consistently published their annual reports and disclosed audit committee composition details over the study period. This ensured the reliability and validity of the data used for analysis.

The study relied entirely on secondary data, primarily obtained from the audited annual reports of the selected companies. These documents were accessed through the official portals of the Nigerian Exchange Group, Ghana Stock Exchange, and individual company websites. The data spanned a period of ten years (2014–2023) and covered variables including audit committee size and market capitalization. Using official regulatory and corporate sources improved the credibility and accuracy of the dataset.

Given the panel structure of the dataset—combining both time-series and cross-sectional data—the study utilized panel regression analysis as the primary analytical tool. This approach enables the model to control for individual firm-level heterogeneity that could otherwise bias the results. Two estimation models were considered: the Fixed Effects Model (FEM) and the Random Effects Model (REM). The Hausman test was used to determine the most appropriate model for the data, ensuring that the estimations account for unobserved but firm-specific characteristics.

In addition to regression analysis, the study performed descriptive statistical analysis to summarize the dataset and understand the underlying distribution of variables. Measures such as mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values were computed. This helped assess the variability and central tendencies in both audit committee size and corporate value across the selected firms. T-tests were employed to evaluate the statistical significance of individual regression coefficients, while F-statistics were used to assess overall model fit. The adjusted R-squared value was reported to indicate the explanatory power of the model.

The study examined the relationship between the audit committee size (independent variable) and firm value (dependent variable).

- Audit Committee Size (ACSZE) was measured as the total number of members serving on a firm's audit committee in a given year. This approach draws on prior studies that link the size of governance structures to oversight effectiveness and firm performance.
- Firm Value (FVAL) was proxied by the market capitalization of each firm, representing the total market value of the company's outstanding shares.

The general functional form of the model is expressed as:

$$FVAL_{it} = f(ACSZE_{it})$$

The econometric model is specified as:

$$FVAL_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACSZE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where:

FVAL_{it} = Corporate value (Market Capitalization) of firm *i* in year *t*

ACSZE_{it} = Audit committee size of firm *i* in year *t*

β₀ = Intercept

β₁ = Coefficient for audit committee size

ε_{it} = Error term

i = Individual firm

t = Time (year)

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

Table 1 Descriptive Analysis

NIGERIA		
	FVAL	ACSZE
Mean	360.2521	5.816667
Median	173.3138	6.000000
Maximum	1310.680	7.000000
Minimum	16.52818	5.000000
Std. Dev.	413.7684	0.567231
Skewness	1.124439	-0.017742
Kurtosis	2.762337	2.824619
Jarque-Bera	12.78483	0.080044
Probability	0.001674	0.960768
Observations	60	60
GHANA		
	FVAL_G	ACSZE_G
Mean	0.347346	3.508475
Median	0.125504	4.000000
Maximum	2.056869	5.000000
Minimum	0.008735	2.000000
Std. Dev.	0.418731	0.626233
Skewness	1.549073	-0.456939
Kurtosis	6.156067	2.725113
Jarque-Bera	48.08319	2.238893
Probability	0.000000	0.326460
Observations	59	59

Source: Eviews Output (2025)

The descriptive statistics comparison in Table 1 shows that Nigerian firms have substantially higher firm values (FVAL) compared to firms in Ghana, with means of 360.25 and 0.35, respectively. Additionally, audit committees in Nigeria tend to be larger, averaging 5.82 members versus 3.51 in Ghana. Firm value distributions are positively skewed in both countries, while the variability, as measured by standard deviation, is generally greater among Nigerian firms for most variables. These findings suggest underlying structural and governance differences that may affect firm value across the two markets.

4.2 Test of hypothesis

H₀₁ Audit Committee Size does not have significant effect on the Firm Value of quoted consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria and Ghana.

H_{A1} Audit Committee Size has a significant effect on the Firm Value of quoted consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria and Ghana.

Table 2 Regression Result (Extract) for Hypothesis One (NIGERIA)

Dependent Variable: FVAL
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 12/01/24 Time: 18:46
 Sample: 2014 2023
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 6
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 60

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ACSZE	-444.0988	162.4348	-2.734012	0.0087
C	5479.122	1705.993	3.211691	0.0023

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025

Table 2 shows that Audit Committee Size (ACSZE) has a negative beta coefficient of (-444.10) and a statistically significant p-value of (0.0087). This means that Audit Committee Size (ACSZE) has a significant negative relationship with Firm Value (FVAL). This implies that an increase in audit committee size negatively affects firm value. A possible interpretation could be that larger committees face coordination challenges, reducing efficiency in quoted consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Table 3: Regression Result Estimate for Hypothesis One (GHANA)

Dependent Variable: FVAL_G
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 12/01/24 Time: 20:35
 Sample: 2014 2023
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 6
 Total panel (unbalanced) observations: 59

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ACSZE_G	0.340392	0.116316	2.926453	0.0052
C	-0.780189	0.825603	-0.944993	0.3494

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025

Table 3 shows that Audit Committee Size (ACSZE_G) has a positive beta coefficient of (0.3404) and a statistically significant p-value of (0.0052). This means that Audit Committee Size (ACSZE_G) has a significant positive relationship with Firm Value (FVAL). This implies that an increase in the size of the audit committee positively impacts firm value in Ghana, potentially due to enhanced oversight and diversity of perspectives.

Hypothesis One Decision

Table 4 Summary of Comparative result for Test of Hypothesis One

	Variable	B	P-value	Individual Country	Decision
NIGERIA	ACSZE	-444.0988	0.0087	Significant	Reject H0 ₁
GHANA	ACSZE_G	0.340392	0.0052	Significant	

Researcher’s Comcept, 2025

Nigeria: The coefficient of ACSZE is -444.10 (negative), with a p-value of 0.0087 (significant as it is less than 0.05). This implies that the relationship between ACSZE and FVAL is negative and significant. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected for Nigeria.

Ghana: The coefficient of ACSZE_G is 0.34 (positive), with a p-value of 0.0052 0087 (significant as it is less than 0.05). This implies that the relationship between ACSZE_G and FVAL is positive and significant. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is also rejected for Ghana.

Decision: The Null Hypothesis which states that Audit Committee Size does not have a significant effect on Firm Value in quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria and Ghana is rejected because the effect of Audit Committee Size is significant on Firm Value in quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria and Ghana.

4.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDING

In Nigeria, the data reveals that the size of the audit committee carries a negative and statistically significant relationship with firm value. The coefficient associated with audit committee size (ACSZE) is -444.0988, with a p-value of 0.0087, indicating a strong likelihood that an increase in committee members correlates with a reduction in firm market capitalization. This outcome suggests that simply increasing the number of audit committee members does not necessarily enhance firm performance. The underlying reasons might include potential inefficiencies, coordination challenges, and higher administrative expenses that accompany larger committees. Larger groups can sometimes suffer from slower decision-making processes or diffusion of responsibility, which may adversely affect firm value. These observations correspond closely with the findings of Omotoye *et al.* (2021), who identified a negative significant relationship between audit committee size and Tobin's Q—a proxy for market performance—in Nigerian deposit money banks. Their research further suggested that while committee size and board size negatively affected market valuation, attributes such as gender diversity and financial expertise within the committee positively influenced firm performance. The implication is that structural weaknesses in governance can diminish firm value. Similarly, Olayikan's (2019) investigation into audit committee effectiveness within Nigerian public banks aligns with these results. In that study, audit committee effectiveness was assessed using metrics such as committee size, meeting frequency, and members' financial literacy. It was found that none of these factors—including committee size—exerted a statistically significant effect on firms' profitability measured by profit before tax. Together, these studies raise important questions about the optimal size of audit committees in Nigeria and the potential drawbacks of increasing committee membership without improving functionality.

Contrasting the Nigerian experience, the study finds a positive and statistically significant association between audit committee size and firm value in Ghana. The coefficient for audit committee size in Ghana (ACSZE_G) is 0.340392 with a p-value of 0.0052, indicating that larger committees tend to coincide with higher market capitalization. This positive relationship suggests that, in the Ghanaian corporate context, bigger audit committees may contribute to stronger oversight, increased investor confidence, and ultimately better governance outcomes. Larger committees might be better equipped to provide diverse expertise, monitor management activities, and reduce agency problems, thereby enhancing firm value. This divergent result between Nigeria and Ghana likely reflects differences in regulatory frameworks, corporate governance culture, and management practices. The Ghanaian finding resonates with the work of Dare *et al.* (2021), who explored the impact of audit committee characteristics on audit quality in Nigeria's oil and gas sector. Their research showed that while audit committee meetings had an insignificant positive effect, audit committee size significantly and positively influenced audit quality. This highlights the possibility that the beneficial effects of committee size are sector or country specific. Additionally, Gbenyi *et al.* (2023) reported complex and sometimes counterintuitive effects of audit committee characteristics on share price reaction in Nigerian deposit money banks. Their study found a mix of negative and significant impacts of committee size, independence, meeting frequency, and gender diversity on share price movements, while financial expertise exhibited a positive but statistically

insignificant influence. These nuances underscore the multifaceted nature of audit committee attributes in different governance environments.

5.0 CONCLUSION

The contrasting effects of audit committee size on firm value in Nigeria and Ghana highlight fundamental differences in how governance structures operate across the two countries. In Nigeria, the significant negative relationship suggests that larger audit committees may be inefficient, potentially leading to coordination challenges, diluted accountability, or decision-making delays that adversely impact firm value. Conversely, in Ghana, the significant positive relationship implies that larger audit committees might enhance oversight capabilities, bring in diverse expertise, and strengthen governance processes, thereby contributing positively to firm valuation. These opposing outcomes suggest that the effectiveness of audit committee size is not universal but context-dependent, influenced by institutional, regulatory, and organizational dynamics unique to each country. Factors such as how committee members are selected, their level of engagement, and the quality of deliberations may determine whether a larger size leads to effective oversight or becomes a burden. The structure and functionality of the committee within each governance environment therefore play a crucial role in determining its impact on firm value.

The findings also underscore that audit committee size, though a structural feature, interacts with deeper operational and cultural variables that can either amplify or undermine its intended benefits. While the statistical significance of the results confirms that size does influence firm value, the direction of this influence differs sharply depending on the national context. This emphasizes the need to move beyond a one-size-fits-all view of corporate governance metrics and consider the embedded realities that shape their outcomes in different jurisdictions.

RECOMMENDATION

1. For Nigerian corporate governance regulators and boards: Given the negative impact of larger audit committees on firm value, regulators and boards should evaluate and potentially enforce limits on the maximum size of audit committees to improve efficiency and accountability.
2. For Ghanaian corporate boards and shareholders: Recognizing the positive influence of larger audit committees on firm value, boards and shareholders should prioritize expanding audit committee membership to enhance oversight quality and bring in diverse expertise that can add value.

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